

Submission to the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women Draft (CEDAW) General Recommendation No. 41: Dismantling Gender Stereotypes and the Unequal Power Relations that Sustain Them

Following the launch of Women in AI Ethics® in 2018 to elevate the voices and work of diverse experts in the AI Ethics space, WAIE+¹ was established in 2025 as a Public Interest AI venture. Through its global expert community, research institute, and media network, WAIE+ builds educational programs and resources to ensure a safe and secure AI future for all of humanity.

WAIE+ welcomes the opportunity to provide comments on the Draft of General Recommendation No. 41 "Dismantling Gender Stereotypes and the Unequal Power Relations that Sustain Them" of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW). As an AI expert community, we have focused our feedback on the sections of the General Recommendation relevant to the human rights impact of the use of AI. Should the Committee have any questions on the comments and recommendations provided in this document, WAIE+ will be pleased to provide additional clarifications.

General note on terminology (applicable in particular to paragraphs 32 and 60)

WAIE+ notes that "**artificial intelligence**" (**AI**) is an umbrella term encompassing a wide range of digital technologies that seek to solve tasks of varying complexity, often through approaches mimicking human thought.² These technologies and approaches include but are not limited to deterministic algorithms, machine learning models, predictive data analytics, neural networks, computer vision, large language models, and image generators.

¹ 'WAIE+ AI Expert Community & Media Network' (*WAIE+ Community*) <<https://www.waieplus.com>>.

² ICO and The Alan Turing Institute, 'Explaining Decisions Made with AI' (ICO 2022) <<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/key-dp-themes/explaining-decisions-made-with-artificial-intelligence/>>

These technologies are developed and deployed differently and thus perpetuate gender stereotypes in different ways.³

WAIE+ recommends **clarifying the scope of the term "artificial intelligence"** in this General Recommendation and stating explicitly that it is a term that can refer to a wide range of technologies. Rather than treating artificial intelligence as a single, undifferentiated category, States parties should be responsive to the specific forms of gender stereotyping perpetuated by different technologies and approaches.

Paragraph 32

WAIE+ welcomes the Committee's attention to the role of digital technology and AI in reproducing and reinforcing gender stereotypes. We offer the following comments to strengthen the paragraph.

First, WAIE+ recommends specifically naming "**predictive analytics**," "**algorithmic decision-making systems**," and "**data-driven decision support systems**," alongside the technologies and approaches already listed. These technologies are used to support or make consequential decisions about people in both the public and private sectors, including decisions about access to social services, employment, credit, healthcare, and child welfare.⁴ Omitting specific discussion of these technologies risks narrowing the Committee's analysis to more visible consumer-facing AI, while systems that are structurally embedded in women's lives remain less visible.

Second, regarding the **public sector** specifically, the obligation under Article 5 of CEDAW to eliminate gender stereotypes should be read in conjunction with the obligations under Article 11 to ensure the right to social security (Art. 11.1(e)) and to social services to enable parents to combine family, work and participation in public life (Art. 11.2(c)) without

³ See for example Abeba Birhane, 'Algorithmic Colonization of Africa' (2020) 17 SCRIPTed 389 <<https://doi.org/10.2966/scrip.170220.389>>; Lena Wang, 'The Three Harms of Gendered Technology' (2020) 24 Australasian Journal of Information Systems <<https://doi.org/10.3127/ajis.v24i0.2799>>; Miruna-Valeria Craiut and Ioana Raluca Iancu, 'Is Technology Gender Neutral? A Systematic Literature Review on Gender Stereotypes Attached to Artificial Intelligence' (2022) 18 Human Technology 297 <<https://doi.org/10.14254/1795-6889.2022.18-3.6>>; Hernan Maina and others, 'Exploring Stereotypes and Biases in Language Technologies in Latin America' (2024) 67 Communications of the ACM <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3653322>>.

⁴ Sarah Myers West, Meredith Whittaker and Kate Crawford, 'Discriminating Systems: Gender, Race, and Power in AI' (AI Now Institute 2019) <<https://ainowinstitute.org/publication/discriminating-systems-gender-race-and-power-in-ai-2>>.

discrimination.⁵ In the public sector, AI technologies used in the provision of public services require the use of **training data** drawn from data collected about individuals and families who have previously interacted with these services,⁶ a practice which increasingly reaches the level of surveillance.⁷ Through this data collection, the complexity of individual and family lives is **simplified** in order to render it legible to individual data systems: as a result of this simplification, the services available to individuals and families are often **based on stereotypes, including stereotypes about gendered roles within the family.**⁸ As a result, social services continue to rely on and perpetuate gender stereotyping rather than eliminating it. WAIE+ therefore recommends that paragraph 32 note that AI systems used in public service delivery reproduce and reinforce gender stereotypes through their reliance on historically biased training data, and that States parties' obligations under Articles 5 and 11 extend to addressing this harm.

Third, WAIE+ recommends that paragraph 32 specifically note that many systems in use in the public and private sectors lack **transparency**, both in where they are used and how they determine outputs from inputs. This makes it difficult to identify where gender stereotypes influence outputs and limits the ability of those affected by harms to seek and obtain an effective remedy.⁹

Fourth, paragraph 32 does not currently address generative AI and **synthetic content**. Generative AI systems, including large language models and image generators, are used to produce content at scale that sexualizes, stereotypes, and degrades women.¹⁰ The proliferation of non-consensual synthetic intimate imagery is a documented and growing harm that connects directly to the paragraph's existing concern with gender-based violence

⁵ UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), 'General Recommendation No. 28 on the Core Obligations of States Parties under Article 2 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women' (2010) UN Doc CEDAW/C/2010/47/GC.2 <<http://www2.ohchr.org/english/bodies/cedaw/docs/CEDAW-C-2010-47-GC2.pdf>>.

⁶ Myers West, Whittaker and Crawford (n 4).

⁷ Laura Carter, 'Prescripted Living: Gender Stereotypes and Data-Based Surveillance in the UK Welfare State' (2021) 10 Internet Policy Review <<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.14763/2021.4.1593>>

⁸ Laura Carter, 'Machine-Readable Lives or "Troubled Families"? Classification, Categorisation and Stereotyping in Data Collection and Sharing in Children's Social Care in England' (doctoral, University of Essex 2023) <<https://repository.essex.ac.uk/36627/>>

⁹ Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 'Algorithmic Accountability for the Public Sector' (2021) <<https://www.opengovpartnership.org/documents/algorithmic-accountability-public-sector/>>.

¹⁰ Aisha Sobey, 'The Thinness of GenAI: Body Size in Relation to the Construction of the Normate through GenAI Image Models' (2025) 5 AI and Ethics 4181 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-025-00684-x>>.

in the digital space.¹¹ WAIE+ therefore recommends that paragraph 32 specifically name generative AI systems and **non-consensual synthetic intimate imagery** as a distinct and documented form of AI-enabled gender-based harm requiring States parties' attention.

Paragraph 38

WAIE+ welcomes the obligation on States parties to identify the conditions and as a means through which stereotypes can manifest, listing constitutions, laws, policies, institutions, systems, services, and practices. WAIE+ recommends **specifically including "digital technologies" and "artificial intelligence systems"** in this list. Given the detailed treatment of AI as a site of stereotyping elsewhere in the General Recommendation, its absence from the means-of-manifestation list in paragraph 38 is a gap that could limit the paragraph's practical application. States parties should understand explicitly that the identification obligation under this paragraph extends to algorithmic and data-driven tools, including those procured from third-party and/or private sector vendors.

Paragraph 48

WAIE+ welcomes the Committee's attention to the specific role played by media entities, including social media, in perpetuating gender stereotypes. In line with our recommendation regarding paragraph 32 above, we recommend the committee notes that engaging with social media is a key method through which States parties can challenge the creation and distribution of **non-consensual synthetic intimate imagery**.

Paragraph 59 (b) and (c)

WAIE+ welcomes the specific recommendations to States parties on engaging with social media. We recommend including that the legislative, regulatory and oversight measures identified in 59(b) and (c) should address the **harms of generative AI to women**, and should include measures prohibiting the creation and distribution of non-consensual synthetic intimate imagery, as well as requirements on platform operators to establish accessible and effective reporting and removal mechanisms for such content, with defined response time obligations.

¹¹ Rebecca Umbach and others, 'Non-Consensual Synthetic Intimate Imagery: Prevalence, Attitudes, and Knowledge in 10 Countries' *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Association for Computing Machinery 2024) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642382>>

Paragraph 60

WAIE+ welcomes the Committee's recommendations on digitalization, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity. We offer the following comments to bring these recommendations into alignment with the **specificity and enforceability standard** the Committee has established in other sectors, including education (paragraph 53), health (paragraph 56), and media (paragraph 59), of this General Recommendation. As currently drafted, the recommendations in paragraph 60 are primarily process-oriented, calling for regulatory frameworks, dialogue mechanisms, and participation initiatives, and do not name specific actors, specific legal reform requirements, or accountability mechanisms for harms beyond digital gender-based violence. WAIE+ therefore recommends the following additions to strengthen paragraph 60 in line with the specificity and enforceability standard applied elsewhere in this General Recommendation.

Section (a)

WAIE+ recommends explicitly including **transparency and explainability** requirements within the proposed recommendation on a gender-responsive, human-rights based and intersectional regulatory framework. States parties should require that AI systems used in consequential decisions affecting women, including in employment, credit, social services, healthcare, and the justice system, meet minimum transparency standards such that affected individuals can understand the basis on which a decision was made and exercise their right to an effective remedy.

Section (b)

WAIE+ recommends strengthening this recommendation through additionally recommending **mandatory, recurrent and gender-sensitive training** on gender stereotypes. We additionally recommend including specific examples of actors to whom **codes of conduct, guidance and mandatory training** should apply: for example, “professionals working in the development, procurement, deployment, auditing, and regulation of AI systems, including those working in technology companies, government agencies deploying AI tools, and regulatory bodies.”

Section (e)

WAIE+ welcomes the recognition that engagement with non-state actors will be crucial in combating gender stereotypes in the digitalization, artificial intelligence and cybersecurity fields. We recommend adding the recommendation that States parties should adopt legislative, regulatory and oversight measures requiring **private sector actors**—including

AI developers, employers, financial institutions, and platform operators—to conduct **gender impact assessments** prior to the release of AI systems intended for use in consequential decisions affecting women. States parties should conduct regular audits of AI tools used in hiring, credit, insurance, content moderation, and similar functions, to identify and remediate outputs that reflect or reinforce gender stereotypes. Audit results should be reported to competent regulatory authorities, and affected individuals should have access to complaint mechanisms and effective remedies.

Section (g)

Given the evidence that the use of data-driven and artificial intelligence technologies—including predictive analytics, algorithmic prioritization and/or decision-making—reinforces gender stereotypes, WAIE+ recommends that para 60(g) should oblige States parties to enact **proactive monitoring and evaluation** of any data-driven or AI tools—whether developed in-house or procured from a third-party vendor—to ensure that they challenge gender stereotyping:

Additional section

WAIE+ recommends specifically including additional recommendations for States parties using **artificial intelligence technologies in the public sector and/or in the delivery of public services**:

(h) Public sector AI and service delivery. States parties have an obligation to deliver public services without gender stereotyping or discrimination. Given the evidence that the use of data-driven and artificial intelligence technologies, including predictive analytics, algorithmic prioritization and/or decision-making, reinforces gender stereotypes in the delivery of public services, with disproportionate impact on women facing intersecting forms of discrimination including on grounds of race, disability, and migration status, States parties should:

- (i) Enact mechanisms for mandatory pre-deployment gender impact assessments for any data-driven or AI tool used in the delivery of public services, whether developed in-house or procured from a third-party vendor, to identify whether the tool reflects or reinforces gender stereotypes *before* it enters use;
- (ii) Collect and publish gender-disaggregated outcome data from AI tools used in public services at regular intervals, to identify where stereotyped outputs are occurring and to inform corrective action;

(iii) Establish clear accountability mechanisms, including accessible complaints procedures for women affected by discriminatory outputs of AI tools used in public services, with obligations on States parties to investigate complaints and provide effective remedies, including revision or suspension of tools found to produce discriminatory outcomes.

This submission has been authored by WAIE+ Fellows Laura Carter and Kristina Kroot.¹²

¹² 'WAIE+ Fellowship Program' (WAIE+ Community) <<https://www.waieplus.com/fellowship>>